

Physico-Chemical Studies of Emulsions : Part III. Mutual Breaking of Emulsions

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Mutual coagulation of lyophobic colloids¹⁻³ and mutual coacervation of lyophilic colloids⁴⁻⁶ have been studied extensively, but no attention has been paid so far on the mutual demulsification or mutual breaking of emulsions that is, conversion into two macroscopic liquid layers by mutual action of emulsions of opposite sign of charge. In continuation of previous work^{7,8} the present investigation reports the mutual demulsification of oppositely charged emulsions stabilized by single surfactants, binary mixtures of surfactants, binary mixtures of protein and surfactants and tertiary mixtures of protein and surfactants and water and kerosene oil as external and internal phases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anionic surfactants : sodium dioctyl sulphosuccinate (MOT) and sodium dibutyl sulphosuccinate (MIB), cationic surfactants : cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB) and cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTMAB) and nonionic surfactant : alkyl aryl polyether alcohol (T×100) were B.D.H. England products and polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (T.60-nonionic surfactant) was obtained from Messrs Koch-Light Laboratories Ltd., London. Gelatin of photographic quality was prepared as described earlier⁹. In all the experiments double distilled kerosene oil (K.O., b.p. 205° and sp.gr., .7948925 at 30°) and double distilled water (pH 6.2 and conductivity $.85 \times 10^{-6}$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) were used.

Preparation of emulsions : Agent-in-water method¹⁰ was employed to prepare emulsions under the following conditions as described earlier⁷ : (a) Definite ratio of K.O. and water; (b) Definite and equal concentrations of emulsifying agents.

Mutual action of emulsions : The procedure followed to find out the ratio of oppositely charged emulsions necessary to cause mutual demulsification is described below with reference to the emulsions stabilized by MOT and CPB.

In nine test tubes of the same size 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 ml. of emulsion stabilized by MOT were placed successively, and to each of these were added in turn 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 ml. of emulsion stabilized by CPB. After each addition the contents were mixed well by inverting the tube three times and then the tubes were placed in a rack for

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TABLE I
Ratio of oppositely charged emulsions necessary to cause mutual demulsification

Emulsion Type:—O/W, O/W ratio : 1 : 2, K.O. = 10 ml., MIB = .05 g., MOT = .05 g., CPB = .05 g., CTMAB = .05 g., T.60 = .05 g., T×100 = .05 g., GEL = .05 g.

(a)	(b) CPB	(c) CPB +T.60	(d) CPB +T×100	(e) CPB +GEL	(f) CPB +T.60 +GEL	(g) CPB +T×100 +GEL	(h) CTMAB	(i) CTMAB +T.60	(j) CTMAB +T×100	(k) CTMAB +GEL	(l) CTMAB +T.60 +GEL	(m) CTMAB +T×100 +GEL
(a) : (b)	(a) : (c)	(a) : (d)	(a) : (e)	(a) : (f)	(a) : (g)	(a) : (h)	(a) : (i)	(a) : (j)	(a) : (k)	(a) : (l)	(a) : (l)	(a) : (m)
MIB	1 : 1	1 : 0.96	1 : 0.92	1 : 0.64	1 : 0.61	1 : 0.58	1 : 0.88	1 : 0.85	1 : 0.81	1 : 0.53	1 : 0.51	1 : 0.49
MIB+T.60	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.04	1 : 1	1 : 0.69	1 : 0.66	1 : 0.63	1 : 0.96	1 : 0.92	1 : 0.88	1 : 0.58	1 : 0.56	1 : 0.53
MIB+T×100	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.08	1 : 0.75	1 : 0.72	1 : 0.69	1 : 1.04	1 : 1	1 : 0.96	1 : 0.63	1 : 0.61	1 : 0.58
MIB+GEL	1 : 1.77	1 : 1.70	1 : 1.63	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.04	1 : 1.63	1 : 1.56	1 : 1.50	1 : 1	1 : 0.96	1 : 0.92
MIB+T.60+GEL	1 : 1.94	1 : 1.85	1 : 1.77	1 : 1.22	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.77	1 : 1.70	1 : 1.63	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.04	1 : 1
MIB+T×100+GEL	1 : 2.12	1 : 2.03	1 : 1.94	1 : 1.32	1 : 1.27	1 : 1.22	1 : 1.94	1 : 1.85	1 : 1.77	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.08
MOT	1 : 1.04	1 : 1	1 : 0.96	1 : 0.66	1 : 0.63	1 : 0.61	1 : 0.92	1 : 0.88	1 : 0.85	1 : 0.56	1 : 0.53	1 : 0.51
MOT+T.60	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.04	1 : 0.72	1 : 0.6	1 : 0.66	1 : 1	1 : 0.96	1 : 0.92	1 : 0.61	1 : 0.58	1 : 0.56
MOT+T×100	1 : 1.22	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.12	1 : 0.78	1 : 0.75	1 : 0.72	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.04	1 : 1	1 : 0.66	1 : 0.63	1 : 0.61
MOT+GEL	1 : 1.85	1 : 1.77	1 : 1.70	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.70	1 : 1.63	1 : 1.56	1 : 1.04	1 : 1	1 : 0.96
MOT+T.60+GEL	1 : 2.03	1 : 1.94	1 : 1.85	1 : 1.27	1 : 1.22	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.85	1 : 1.77	1 : 1.70	1 : 1.12	1 : 1.08	1 : 1.04
MOT+T×100+GEL	1 : 2.22	1 : 2.12	1 : 2.03	1 : 1.38	1 : 1.32	1 : 1.27	1 : 2.03	1 : 1.94	1 : 1.85	1 : 1.22	1 : 1.17	1 : 1.12

six hours. At the end of six hours, it was found that almost complete breaking had taken place in the tube having emulsions mixed in equal proportions. Thus the mutual demulsification value was between 4 to 6 ml. of emulsion stabilized by MOT and 6 to 4 ml. of emulsion stabilized by CPB. To find out the complete breaking ratio, further experiments were performed in narrow ranges pretty close to 1 : 1 proportion. It was observed that 4.9 ml of MOT emulsion and 5.1 ml of CPB emulsion were required to cause complete breaking of emulsions into two separate phases. The mutual demulsification ratio is, therefore, 1 : 1.04 in the present case.

The above procedure was adopted with other emulsions and the results are summarised in Table I

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results given in Table I indicate that the order of stability of anionic surfactants and their mixtures towards mutual demulsification by cationic surfactants and their mixtures is : MIB < MOT < MIB+T.60 < MOT+T.60 < MIB+T×100 < MOT+T×100 < MIB+GEL < MOT+GEL < MIB+T.60+GEL < MOT+T.60+GEL < MIB+T×100+GEL < MOT+T×100+GEL.

Similarly, the order of stability of cationic surfactants and their mixtures towards mutual breaking of emulsions by anionic surfactants and their mixtures is : CPB < CTMAB < CPB+T.60 < CTMAB+T.60 < CPB+T×100 < CTMAB+T×100 < CPB+GEL < CTMAB+GEL < CPB+T.60+GEL < CTMAB+T.60+GEL < CPB+T×100+GEL < CTMAB+T×100+GEL.

The cause of mutual demulsification is probably electrical interaction between the ions constituting the double layers of the respective emulsions. The presence of ions of an emulsifying agent which are of opposite charge to that of another, results in a decrease in the numerical value of zeta potential which when decreased below the critical value, the repulsions between approaching particles are reduced and the colliding particles join together causing demulsification.

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